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Modern Techniques for Creating a Positive Family Institution Image in the Republic of Bashkortostan

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Abstract

The relevance of the presented problems is due to the fact that nowadays the social policy priority directions of the Russian Federation and the Republic of Bashkortostan in particular are strengthening the family institution, the formation of its positive image, maintaining the spiritual and moral traditions of family relations, family life and education. The purpose of the article is to develop modern techniques for creating a positive family institution image in the Republic of Bashkortostan. Based on the data of numerous studies, the authors presented the family institution current state in the region, as well as the experience analysis of the Republic, the leading trends in the field of family policy in the region. The article presents a theoretical analysis of the family institution image forming mechanisms, offers expert-analytical and axiological approaches to the search and implementation of opportunities and ways to improve the image and predict their effectiveness; it considers the leading directions of the University's activities on psychological and pedagogical support of the student family and childhood; it offers techniques for forming a positive family image. The research theoretical and methodological basis includes analytical and predictive as well as project methods. They allow us to consider this problem as a purposeful and organized process of forming a positive family institution image. There are psychological, pedagogical, methodological and technological materials in this article. It can be useful to scientists, teachers, managers in the field of family policy and pedagogy, social workers, as their activities are designed to ensure the preservation and development of family values and value orientations.

Keywords: institution of the family, family image, family policy, family values, family axiosphere, national idea, family development.

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Introduction

The family crisis problems, family values destruction and related demographic problems are currently in the focus of attention of the world community and state, social, political and scientific institutions.

It is no coincidence that one of the primary state tasks today is to form in the citizens' minds a positive family institution image. It should include the marriage preservation priority, mutual love and marital commitment; they aim to encourage the birth and upbringing of children, the desire for large families; they want children to respect their parents and elders, make them feel heirs of the family history, traditions and nation in general.

Therefore, we need to create favourable conditions to preserve and develop the family and family relations value priorities, to integrate educational, scientific and methodological resources aimed at training a competent specialist of a new type in the conditions of family development and family relations; we need to design innovative models and techniques of psychological and pedagogical support for parenthood and childhood; it is imperative to coordinate scientific and network projects in the context of the family problems and family relations study in the region, which ultimately guarantees the positive family image formation success.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The research purpose is to theoretically justify and experimentally test the effectiveness of the developed techniques for creating a positive family institution image (through the example of the Republic of Bashkortostan).

Literature review

The study of the family, its problems and prospects for development is one of the most advanced areas of the modern science. Family is a fundamental element of any society. It has a direct impact on its comprehensive development by reproducing the population, enriching tangible and spiritual values, forming the character and spiritual experience of the future society citizens. For any society, the family institution and the ability to support is of primary importance, because countries that had strong moral and family foundations also thrived economically.

Traditionally, the family policy is considered as a part of the social policy that includes measures to influence the family, processes of family change, or family behavior. Modern researchers Antonov (1980), Arkhangelsky et al. (2017), Medkov (2002) interpret this term as an activity aimed at developing the family, family lifestyle, family culture, strengthening family social functions as one of the main society institutions.

The federal and regional family policy level correlation issues were in the focus of attention of Darmodekhin (2014), Luneva et al. (2019). The main topics discussed by researchers are the lack of family policy independence in the state's internal policy, family policy's controversial nature, moreover, a regional unit implements the family policy as a separate unit, etc.

However, the image of the Russian family is formed precisely through the implementation of the family policy. The modern Russian family is significantly different from the traditional one and, according to modern researchers, it is in a crisis stage. They negatively assess that it either lost its basic functions or had them replaced by state and public institutions, social and cultural traditions of a large family and family lifestyle were destroyed. In addition, the authors note the elimination of family production, which is predominant in the social economy, a family lifestyle, crowding out all family members into the sphere, hired labor, replacing the joint activities of parents and children with individual self-care and consumption, focusing the activities of all social institutions on a single person. This is partly confirmed by the statistics.

According to Troshkina and Smolina (2019), apparently with no proper support at the stage of formation, including the state support, 60% of families break up in the first 5 years of marriage. Overcoming the crisis is impossible without the help of the state.

The problem of forming a positive family image among modern young people - both in terms of their structural content and in the genetic aspect - seems extremely urgent in connection with the seemingly rapid change in the family itself, its psychological and sociological parameters. The changes have been multiply noted by researchers.

This article presents approaches to understanding the modern family phenomenon from the side of social ideas about it formed amongst students.

First of all, our study's methodology was the social images provisions by Moscovici. He defined social images as a system of values, ideas and activities (actions) with a double function: firstly, establishing an order [systematization], which will allow people to navigate their material and social life and master it

[orientation and adaptation]; and secondly, communicating with members of society by providing them with a code for social exchange and a code for the unambiguous name and classification of their history various aspect (individual and group ones) (Duveen et al., 1990, p. 1).

Among the Russian studies of family images performed in a structural approach, we can note a study dedicated to the family image representations differences among children and parents and carried out under the guidance of Shvetsova and Sobchenko (2018). We can note a research by Bondaletov and Budylna (2014).

Shvetsova and Sobchenko (2018, p. 40) believe that it was shown that the core ideas content about the family (“love, home, parents, happiness” concept) remains unchanged for modern parents and their children; differences are found in the periphery judgements: young people focus on the sensory and emotional sphere, while “for parents’ generation the dominance is referred to the “home” concept”.

In this regard, the sociological study results by Bondaletov and Budylna (2014) are interesting. They showed that “in modern Russia, there is an obvious tendency to shift the views of young people about the values of marriage towards approaching the spiritual and moral guidelines that dominated the views of young people about marriage a quarter of a century ago” (2014, p. 93-94), in contrast to the more pragmatic family and marital values of the generation that grew up in the 1990s.

In terms of methodology, the works of Kiryakova (2016) in the field of pedagogical axiology are also interesting. They allow to reveal not only values formation nature, including the value orientations of young people, but also to develop the family values development stages among students. Reliance on theoretical and methodological principles of pedagogical axiology provided the simulation of the family axiosphere behind the psycho-pedagogical conditions, methods and techniques of family value orientations formation among students as the basis for a positive family image.

Methodology

We conducted experimental work at the Bashkir State Pedagogical University n.a. M. Akmulla (Ufa, Russia).

The study was conducted in three stages:

- at the first stage we analyzed the family policy current state in the region and the family education theory and practice development degree; and also a research methodology program was developed; the level of

technological and methodological support of family values forming process of young people was identified, the specificity and features of the use of methods and techniques for the family image forming in the region were determined;

- at the second stage we developed and implemented a family axiosphere model and a set of pedagogical conditions for its implementation; experimental work was carried out to verify the effectiveness of the developed methods for the development of students' family values and techniques for forming a positive family image in them;

- at the third stage systematization, comprehension and generalization of the research results were identified; theoretical conclusions were specified; processing and presentation of the study results were identified.

Results

Our statistical studies analysis of Russian and regional sociologists and scientists reveals the deep social and spiritual and moral problems of the family and family relations. The family lifestyle dilution, the motherhood, fatherhood and childhood prestige decline, the family institution image change, the rise of new "social" family viruses (childfree, concubinage, reborn, etc.) are still interesting to the most researchers.

The numbers convincingly show that over the past decade, according to Bashkortostanstat, the birth rate in the Republic dropped to 11.6 (per 1000 people for 9 months of 2017) compared with the figures in the Russian Federation - 12.1. According to the data provided by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Bashkortostan (2017), the age of parenthood has changed significantly: mothers average age at the birth of the first child in 2016 was 25.7 years, of the second child is 29.3 years and the third is 32.6 years. The proportion of births at older ages (from 30 to 40 years or more) has increased significantly. Such indicators as low birth rate, high infant mortality, an increase in children with congenital diseases and early disability, negative changes in reproductive behavior of the population, dilution of family values, instability of the family and marriage situation reveal the harsh realities that characterize the state of the family institution in the Republic of Bashkortostan today.

Meanwhile, a clear understanding of the importance of the identified problem is not always a guarantee of its effective solution in the indicated way. Unfortunately, in scientific pedagogy, even the desired category "image of a prosperous or happy family" does not cause proper research interest among scientists and teachers of family pedagogy.

Categorical and conceptual analysis of the problem under the study allowed us to borrow from sociologists and psychologists the definition of “image” as an image formed in the public or individual consciousness by means of mass communication and psychological influence.

Undoubtedly, the family institution image today is formed as a result of the implementation of the Federal and regional family policies, the activities of the media, educational organizations, public associations, etc.

In confirmation of this, we are happy to see a legitimate shift in regional policy from the family social protection position to the development of its axiosphere as a priority task of the Republic. Organizational and substantive changes in the Ministry of Family, Labor and Social Protection of the Republic of Bashkortostan testify to this positive change in priorities. Its renaming clearly shows a shift in emphasis from the family social protection to creating conditions for the full development of its value principles.

At the same time, we believe that family policy is highly effective when it is equally effectively and positively reflected in the public consciousness of the population. However, the social relations development genesis in the region shows that over the past decades, public consciousness has undergone not only destructive processes of a financial, economic and social and ecological nature, but also has turned out to be in the perspective of the destructive impact of technocratism, pragmatism and the orientation of human on the consumer market. All this naturally led to the dilution of the moral values of society, the weakening of the consolidating role of the family and the devaluation of family values, which ultimately negatively affected the demographic situation in the region.

It is no coincidence, as mentioned above, that in recent years the maximum birth rate has shifted from the age group of 20-24 to 25-29 years, according to the results of a sociological study of demographic behavior of young people conducted in 18 regions of Russia. The following are data from the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Bashkortostan (2017).

The analysis of documentary and scientific and methodological sources in the field of the Republic family policy has convincingly shown that most managers see a constructive way out of this situation. It is the recognition of the family institution as an absolute value in the system of universal and ethno-national relations. In this regard, family education occupies a special place, which we consider as climbing, adapting and integrating a person in the family microcommunity, mastering family orientations, as a process of self-development and self-actualization of a person in the context of family values and relationships. This is confirmed by the study of Islamova, Politaeva and Hajrtdinova (2018).

Based on this, scientists and teachers of the Bashkir State Pedagogical University named after M. Akmulla in their activities are guided by such priorities of the Republic's family policy as the revival and development of value orientations of the family and family relations, the formation of a positive family image and, finally, the psychological and pedagogical support of young families, in particular students' families.

The problem of forming a positive family image was investigated by us in accordance with the following levels:

- analytical and predictive level, including statistical data analysis on the family policy state in the region, documentary and scientific and methodological sources base analysis in the field of family policy and pedagogy in the Republic, a categorical and conceptual analysis of the researched problem;
- organizational and informative level, where we described and developed psychological and pedagogical principles and conditions for the formation of a positive family image, defined the family axiosphere and developed mechanisms for the development of family values and value orientations among students;
- implementational technological level where we developed and implemented methods, tools and technologies for the formation of a positive family image at the University.

At the analytical and predictive level of the study, a social survey was conducted. It revealed the narrowness of young people's ideas about a prosperous family and the lack of ideas about the true values of the family. Thus, to the question "What are families created for?" almost 35% of respondents said that families are needed "to avoid being alone" and "to have a stable partner and assistant nearby" and only 19.7% expressed the opinion that families are created "for the purpose of procreation".

The results analysis of a survey among young people about the desire to have children and their number in the family illustrated a convincing picture of the obvious deformation of views and ideas of young people about the family and family relations. The answer "Yes, but not now" was chosen by the overwhelming majority of respondents (62.5%); "Yes, in the near future" - only 16.7%. At the same time, it is important to note that among the respondents, the greater half was limited by the desire to have only one child. This data was provided by the Federal State Statistics Service (2019).

In this context, researchers of traditional family values are no longer puzzled by the results of a survey in which 32% of respondents admit extramarital affairs and betrayal of spouses depending on family circumstances.

These indicators convincingly illustrate the dilution of traditional family values. Unfortunately, the desire for multiple children, as sociologists correctly note, remains embedded only at the “genetic” level in the minds of a small number of young people.

As part of the study’s organizational and substantive level, we conducted the practical activities in order to form a positive family image in the following areas: parent education; organization of parental and children’s leisure on weekends; distribution and broadcasting in the media and MCT information about families - standards; systematic presentation and coverage of the results of state support for families; propaganda of family values among the middle and older population; organization of direct contacts with families - carriers of a positive image, both among themselves and with other members of society.

Of course, we were aware that television, film production, multimedia, mass media, etc., have a significant impact on the family image formation. But we assumed that the leading role in the positive family image formation is played by a teacher (educator, psychologist). From our point of view, it was a teacher who was assigned the noble mission to be a vehicle of the culture of family relations, to introduce children and parents to the values and traditions of the family, to be the bearer of his or her own family man culture and the inspirer of the family education foundations formation among the younger generation.

In organizing the activities of the teacher, we proceeded from the firm belief that it is necessary to start family education with a return to the first meanings and primary values, which is possible only on the basis of restoring its value representations and relationships.

Based on this, the students’ family values began to form from the first year. For this purpose, the first-year humanitarian disciplines were filled with content and methods of a predominantly social and educational nature, aimed at forming the values of a citizen and a bearer of family and clan traditions (Shezhere, Mother’s Letter, Parent Saturdays, Pedagogical Dynasties and etc. projects). As a part of the pedagogical module disciplines, students first learned how to design their life strategies and tactics, then built a trajectory of personal, social and professional growth for the coming years. As a part of the self-designing of their lives, they were already puzzled in the first courses of plans for the development of their parental solvency, mastering the skills of a healthy lifestyle as the basis of family well-being.

The technological level of the family values formation implies the following stages: students’ awareness of the universal, dominant and priority values of the ethno-national family; recognition of the system of universal, dominant and priority family values; the appropriation of this system of family values; self-transformation based on the acquired system of family value orientations; self-designing the personality of the future teacher in accordance with the assigned family values; mastering the technique of awareness,

recognition and appropriation of family values by children of different ages; designing the process of forming family values for children of different ages, designing and developing programs with a focus on family values. In our understanding, this is the road map for the modern family axiosphere formation.

At the same time, it is very important for a university that a modern student learns to express himself or herself in all the variety of social and personal positions: as a designer of models and technologies for creating a positive family image, as an educator of the family axiosphere in the parental environment, as an organizer of family events and actions in the region, coordinator of interdisciplinary psychological and pedagogical support of the family, as an organizer of monitoring the development of family values, as a teacher of a new type of generation with an established scale of family values and finally, as the bearer of family values. From these positions, a student is formed with innovative thinking and a new attitude to the institution of the family as a value, and, according to Politaeva (2015, p. 126) “pedagogical innovation provides the creation of technologies and ways of influencing the personality, ensuring a balance between social and individual needs, and, thanks to self-development, the individual’s readiness to realize his or her own individuality and the changes in society”.

Thanks to the efforts of the authors of this article today the Bashkir State Pedagogical University is a real platform for developing social and educational projects such as “Garden – for young student’s family”, “Nursery – for young student’s family”, “Mobile kindergarten” as a form of support for student families, family Saturday as a form of parent education and interactive development of children, a group of temporary stay of children using elements of the Montessori method. Students and teachers take part not only in the development of the projects themselves, but also work in the social and cultural facilities created by them. So, the leading methodologists of the Kotoffkids Competency Development Center are masters; educators and assistants in working with children are bachelors. At these sites, not only social and cultural practices are organized, but also practical classes, workshops, trainings for parents, educational games for children, etc. are held. The models of psychological and pedagogical support of young families developed by methodologists are successfully extrapolated to educational, industrial, and medical institutions of the Republic.

We connect our prospects not only with the preparation of competitive personnel for the social and educational sphere of the Republic, but also with the integrated influence on the social and cultural sphere of the region as a whole. Today, the university organically fits into the existing social and educational infrastructure, becoming, in fact, a scientific, methodological and educational center for the training and retraining of teachers in the region.

In order to successfully form a positive family image, the institute has tested modern techniques for integrating the scientific, educational, industrial and public resources of the Republic. For example, the work of student musicians and choreographers in the Maestro children's studio or pre-school students in the Higher School of Childhood provides an opportunity to work out the professional positions of an analyst, designer, forecaster and researcher in the field of family and childhood.

This makes it possible to develop joint research and networking projects of teachers and students, and to participate in the work of the Institute of ideal parents, diagnostic and consulting centers for children and parents, competence development centers, etc.

The implemented projects can definitely be called social and cultural, because in addition to the educational function, the creative teams of teachers and methodologists carry out the ideas of the concept of "Reviving the family through art and culture", "Development of social and cultural practices at the university", etc.

We clearly realize that for the innovative development of family policy in the region we need plenty of experts, managers, marketers, teachers and educators who are able to transform all segments of family education in society. In this regard, the authors group of researchers predicted the task of preparing the future teacher as a person, designed to create conditions conducive to the revival and development of the value priorities of the family and family relationships.

It is important to emphasize here that the success of solving this problem is largely predetermined by how much the university realizes itself in the following positions:

- an integrator of administrative, educational, scientific and methodological resources aimed at training a competent specialist of a new type in conditions of family development and family relations;
- a moderator of transformative processes in the region, providing the development and design of innovative models and techniques of psychological and pedagogical support for parenthood and childhood;
- a coordinator of the potentials and resources of education, production, science, public funds in line with the formation of a positive family image;
- a coordinator of scientific and methodological resources for the development and implementation of scientific and network projects in the context of the study of family problems and family relations in the region.

The historical and genetic analysis of the family policy and upbringing in the Republic showed that since ancient times the peoples of the Bashkir area have been characterized by a commitment to the trinity of national ideas as a key condition for their progressive development. In the pre-revolutionary era, it was the trinity of religious and spiritual faith (Orthodoxy, Islam, Buddhism, etc.); collegiality and autocracy. In the post-revolutionary time, peoples adhered to the trinity of ideological and political faith (communism, socialism, internationalism); collectivism as a reflection of historical and genetic collegiality and community, and, finally, great power, in the symbiosis of which the successful development of the peoples of the region was ensured. We believe that the Republic also found a way out of the post-perestroika crisis in the trinity of spirituality, dignity and sovereignty of modern Russia. However, the nations of Bashkortostan in the process of their development rarely put at the forefront of key national ideas the system-forming role of the family and family values.

Meanwhile, the historical experience of the people's survival has repeatedly shown convincing examples when the family became a consolidating link in the unity of clans and ethnic groups on the path of survival and society development. Now in the era of increasing globalization, many countries especially need to adjust their national goals aimed at strengthening the family and family values. In this regard, the constructive experience of socio-economic development of Belarus is indicative, which proclaimed the triune idea of "Family - Unity – Fatherland", defining the leading focus of its National Development Program on strengthening the spiritual and moral foundations of the family, reviving and promoting family values and traditions. In the eloquent and expressive slogan "Family today is our 'Brest Fortress'", there is a mobilization call to save the family from the demographic threat of the disappearance of the original peoples of the multinational republic ("The National Program of Demographic Security of the Republic of Belarus").

In this context, the focus of the Republic of Bashkortostan on strengthening the family and family values as a priority task acquires special significance. It is noteworthy that the studentship, as the most receptive and mobile community, by its nature is prone to volunteer activities, they heatly responded to the timely provisions of the government regarding progressive family policy. The students involved in our experimental work on the research problem were particularly active in this regard. There are two tendencies of the studentship. The first one proclaims the idea of a family (Rus. "семья") in its homonym in Russian "Seven I" (Rus. "Семь Я"). The second tendency proclaims the idea of volunteering, that is embodied in the abbreviation Three Ds, that means in Russian "Do good deeds" (Rus. "Делаем добрые дела"). These two ideas merged in the deep and accurate youth slogan "Seven I in three Ds" (Rus. "Семь Я в три Д"), which has been the leitmotif of interuniversity student events and projects of the Republic for many years.

From our point of view, starting with studentship, the cult of the family should emerge as the forerunner of the national ideal, as a condition for the formation of a positive family image, as the possibility of proclaiming the family as the absolute value of society, which will ultimately become the leading national idea of the republic, the goal and criterion for successful development of the peoples of Bashkortostan.

Discussions

At the experimental work beginning, it was found that indicators such as low birth rate, high infant mortality, an increase in children with congenital diseases and early disability, a negative change in the reproductive behavior of the population, erosion of family values, and instability of the family-marriage situation characterize the current state of the family institution. It was also determined that the level of technological and methodological support of family values forming process of young people is insufficient. As a result of the introduction of the family axiosphere model and the complex of pedagogical conditions for its implementation, as well as the developed methods for the development of students' family values and the techniques for forming a positive family image, significant positive changes were revealed in young people from the position of a value attitude to the family and the formation of the image of the family institution.

Conclusion

Thus, the most important tool for effective family policy and family pedagogy is the technique of creating a positive image of the Russian family - an emotionally-colored image-representation that contains a stereotypical core that combines the most significant characteristics of the family, revealing its educational potential, personal characteristics and emotional perception of family members, especially the family situation, the potential for vitality and social status. The family institution image structure can be represented as a system of components: family standards, values and value orientations are the central element, under the influence of which the following elements are formed: the composition and structure of the family, the standard of family living, family lifestyle and its psychological microclimate.

The ultimate goal of the family institution image forming is to consolidate the positive family institution image in the citizens' minds. A positive family institution image can be understood as an image of a family that functions as a viable system consisting of a married couple of biological parents and having at least two children of their own, who are provided with adequate social and psychological conditions for development. The basis of the functioning of such a system is the "traditional" family standards, values and value orientations: financial and spiritual responsibility of a man for his family, his work and management of family life; motherhood and family care for a woman; priority of preserving marriage; mutual love and

spouses' commitment; the birth and upbringing of children as the primary life task, the desire for large families; children's respect for their parents and elders, their sense of succession to history, the traditions of the family and the people as a whole. If citizens have or do not have such a family institution image in their minds, it allows us to form a general idea of what the family institution image is nowadays and what adjustments should be made to the implemented family policy.

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